

ELECTRICAL DISCHARGE MACHINING OF CUBIC BORON NITROGEN LAMINATED BLADE

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ABSTRACT

The super-hard materials with high wear-resistances, such as cubic boron nitrogen and polycrystalline diamond, are the best materials for cutting tools. It is very difficult to machine these materials with the conventional grinding and finishing techniques. Productivity is low and costs are high. The electrical discharge machining technique leads to a great increase in productivity and a significant reduction in cost. This paper discusses our research on the characteristics of EDM techniques and the applications of EDM techniques for machining the super-hard materials.

KEYWORDS: Laminated blade; Igniting pulse power; EDM characteristics; Discharge channel.

1. INTRODUCTION

Various kinds of super-intensive and super-hard materials, such as alloy steel, tungsten carbide and ceramic, have been widely used in many industries. In order to machine these materials, super-hard material cutting tools must be used. Usually, super-hard materials such as cubic boron nitrogen, polycrystalline diamond and carborundum are almost as hard as diamond but have higher wear-resistances than diamond. Thus they have been widely used to make cutting tools, drills for petroleum well logging and geological explorations, and wire-drawing dies. The increased demand for super-hard material products causing an increased demand for super-hard cutting tools used for manufacturing industry.

The conventional methods for making cutting tools from hard materials are cutting or grinding with diamond wheels, which is to "overcome hard with hardness". As we know, the hardness of the machined materials is quite close to the hardness of diamond. The machining thus becomes very difficult. In the machining process, the productivity is low and a lot of expensive diamond materials are consumed. For a long time, the costs for making super-hard material cutting tools have been very high, and therefore the prices of these cutting tools also have been very high.

We applied an alternative method for machining cubic boron nitrogen cutting tools which avoids using machining materials made of super-hard materials. We use electrical discharge machining (EDM) to machine super-hard materials. The machining material we used is red copper which is very cheap compare with diamond cutting or grinding wheels. We designed and built a special high energy and high intensity igniting pulse power supply which is used only for the electrical discharge machining of super-hard materials including cubic boron nitrogen, polycrystalline synthetic diamond and carborundum. We then built an EDM device with the special power supply. Our machining method has been successfully used in industry and greatly reduced the manufacturing costs of super-hard material cutting tools.

In this paper, we discuss the EDM characteristics of cubic boron nitrogen, the machining technique we used and the applications of the technique.

2. THE EDM CHARACTERISTICS OF CUBIC BORON NITROGEN LAMINATED BLADE

Super-hard materials can be used to make many kinds of tools. Some of the tools are made of one piece of material, others are made from laminated blades. Usually, a wiredrawing die is made of one piece of polycrystalline diamond or cubic boron nitrogen, and a cutting tool or a drill used in well logging is made from laminated blades. A laminated blade consists of a polycrystalline synthetic diamond or cubic boron nitrogen sheet of one millimeter thick sintered with a tungsten carbide sheet of five millimeter thick. A cubic boron nitrogen laminated blade is shown in Figure 1. And a cutting tool made

FIGURE 1. A cubic boron nitrogen laminated blade (X4)

FIGURE 2. A cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool

of cubic boron nitrogen is shown in Figure 2. The cutting tool consists of two parts: a composite blade and a steel tool body on which the laminated blade is soldered.

Cubic boron nitrogen, tungsten carbide, steel and binding agents used for binding these super-hard materials differ significantly from each other on many physical properties, such as melting point, boiling point and heat conductivity. The differences in physical properties of different materials lead to different EDM characteristics, which makes it very difficult to apply EDM techniques on the cubic boron nitrogen laminated blade. Some of the EDM characteristics are discussed below.

2.1 Discharge Voltage of the Working Gap

We used a copper tool-electrode to machine different materials in kerosene medium and measured the EDM working gap discharge voltages. Some of the results are shown in Table 1. The working gap discharge voltages for the cubic boron nitrogen is almost twice the discharge voltages for steel and red copper. cubic boron nitrogen has very poor electrical conductivities and high melting and boiling points, which makes it difficult to puncture the media in the process of electrical discharge machining. During electrical discharging, the voltage decrement of the surface of cubic boron nitrogen is high. Consequently, the discharge voltage at the working gap is much higher than that of other materials.

TABLE 1 THE WORKING GAP DISCHARGE VOLTAGE OF
SEVERAL MATERIALS

Material	Working Gap Discharge Voltage (V)	Discharge Peak Current (A)	Pulse Duration (μ S)	Pulse Interval (μ S)
Polycrystalline diamond	28	8	120	80
Carborundum	20	8	120	80
Cubic Boron Nitrogen	30	8	120	80
Tungsten Carbide	18	8	120	80
Steel	15	8	120	80
Aluminium	15	8	120	80
Red Copper	14	8	120	80

2.2 Electrical Parameters of the Pulse Power

Usually, cubic boron nitrogen has high electrical resistance and high working gap discharge voltages. Therefore, high working voltages must be applied by the electric power supply during EDM process. Figure 3 shows the relationship between the peak value of working gap voltage V (V) and the machining velocity (or removal rate) V_w during electrical discharge cutting a cubic boron nitrogen laminated blade with

0.8mm width of seam. The machining velocity is defined as the depth (mm) penetrated by the red copper electrode into the die per minute.

FIGURE 3. The relationship between the peak value of working gap voltage and machining velocity during EDM a cubic boron nitrogen laminated blade

Figure 4 shows the relationship between the peak value of the working gap voltage V and machining velocity V_w during electrical discharge grinding (EDG) a cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool. The machining velocity is defined as the volume (mm^3) removed per minute; the copper wheel used for EDG spins at 300 rpm; the stroke of table which fixates the cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool is 36 mm. The number of strokes per minute is 24. In figure 3, we can see the machining situation is similar to machining the cubic boron nitrogen laminated blade with EDM.

In both Figure 3 and 4, the machining velocity is very low or non-existing when peak voltage is under 200V. As peak voltage rises, the condition for a spark discharge is improved and the energy in each electric pulse is increased. Therefore, the machining velocity is also increased. When the peak voltage is higher than 650V, the machining velocity is not increased with the peak voltage. To machine the cubic boron nitrogen which requires high energy and short pulse duration, the time interval between two consecutive pulses should be long enough for deionization.

2.3 Avoiding Arc

The high working voltage used for EDM a workpiece made of cubic boron nitrogen causes a very high temperature in the discharge channel which can often cause arc and burning near the completion of machining a workpiece. When an arc occurs in EDM, the surface of a workpiece can be damaged. Therefore, it is imperative to avoid arc in EDM. Arcs can be prevented by using good pulse power supplies, choosing proper electrical parameters, and improving gap detective systems and tool-electrode servo

FIGURE 4. The relationship between the peak value of working gap voltage and machining velocity during EDG a cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool.

feeding systems. It is also important to keep the working medium clean.

3. PULSE POWER FOR MACHINING CUBIC BORON NITROGEN

From the discussions above, the EDM pulse power supply used for machining cubic boron nitrogen must supply high peak value working voltage and high intensity energy. The regular pulse power supplies are usually not powerful enough for electrical discharge machining these super-hard materials.

Based on a lot of experiments, we designed a special igniting pulse power supply for machining cubic boron nitrogen. The schematics of the igniting power supply is shown in Figure 5. Compare with a regular pulse power supply, our igniting power supply has a higher peak value of working voltage and a faster electrical energy transmission system. In the discharge circuit, we put an energy storage controlled by a computer, the igniting pulse power (in figure 5), which stores high energy. When the EDM working medium is punctured and a discharge channel is formed, the igniting pulse

power releases the stored energy immediately. The high intensity electrical energy causes shocks and exploding which remove the cubic boron nitrogen on the working piece. The igniting pulse power supply we designed can be used for electrical discharge drilling, cavity sinking, grinding, cutting and other EDM applications.

4. RESULT EVALUATIONS OF EDM

FIGURE 5. Schematics of igniting pulse power

We have obtained good results when we used the igniting pulse power for EDM to machine cubic boron nitrogen and tungsten carbide. The working medium we used was kerosene. Table 2 shows the machining time and surface roughness when EDM was used to cut a piece of cubic boron nitrogen.

TABLE 2 MACHINING RESULTS OF EDM

W × L × depth (mm)	Machining Time (min)	Machining Surface Roughness Ra (μm)
0.8 × 13 × 1.8	2.5	2 ~ 0.8
0.8 × 13 × 2.5	4	2 ~ 0.8
0.8 × 13 × 2.5	7	2 ~ 0.8

With electrical discharge grinding, we machined some cutting tools made of cubic boron nitrogen and tungsten carbide. The EDG pulse duration for machining cubic boron nitrogen was 12 microseconds. Figure 6 shows the electrical discharge ground cubic boron nitrogen surface under an electrical microscope. After electrical discharge grinding, the surface roughness was Ra0.08 micro-meter for tungsten carbide, and was Ra0.34 micro-meter. for cubic boron nitrogen. The results of irradiating the surface of cubic boron nitrogen ground by EDM with X-rays indicated that the diffractive intensity of the crystal structure of these super-hard materials did not change.

FIGURE 6. The surface of an electrical discharge ground cubic boron nitrogen under an electrical microscope

FIGURE 7. An electrical discharge machined cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool

After electrical discharge grinding, the cubic boron nitrogen cutting tools had been finished a few times. Figure 7 shows an electrical discharge machined cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool. The cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool machined by EDM was used to cut tungsten carbide die and also obtained very good results. The machining condition was: diameter of workpiece was 13 mm; feed setting was 0.1 mm / rev; cutting depth was 0.2 mm; rotational speed was 840 rpm; cutting speed was 92.3 m / min. The surface roughness of workpiece (made of tungsten carbide) was Ra0.32 micro-meters after the cut. We also use the cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool to machine the workpiece made of ceramics, and obtained good results too.

The quench steel is one of the hard materials. It is difficult to be machined with tungsten carbide cutting tool. But it is no difficult to be machined when we use the cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool machined by EDM. The lifetime of a cubic boron nitrogen cutting tool is almost 60 times longer than that of a tungsten carbide cutting tool.

Our research work indicates that it is possible to machine the super-hard materials such as polycrystalline diamonds and cubic boron nitrogen with EDM. Compare with the conventional cutting and grinding techniques, electrical discharge machining techniques reduce greatly the machining cost for products made of super-hard materials. Because of when we use the EDM techniques to machine these super-hard materials, the tool material which to be consumed in the EDM process is very cheap. It is

only a little material of red copper, and a lot of expensive diamond grinding wheels is to be saved.

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